

Isolation and characterization of hydroxo aqua and μ -dihydroxobisethylenediaminecobalt(III) analogue with biguanide ($\text{BigH}/\text{C}_2\text{H}_7\text{N}_5$)

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Manuscript received 22 October 2009, revised 5 May 2010, accepted 6 May 2010

Abstract : Mono and dinuclear complexes of biguanide (BigH) with cobalt(III) of compositions $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]\text{X}\cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$, where $\text{X} = 2\text{Cl}^-, \text{SO}_4^{2-}$ and $n = 1$ or 2 , $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{NH}_3)_2](\text{SO}_4)_3\cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and μ -dihydroxotetrakisbiguanidinedicobalt(III) $[(\text{Big})_2\text{Co}(\text{OH})_2\text{Co}(\text{Big})_2]$, where $\text{Big} = \text{C}_2\text{H}_6\text{N}_5$ have been prepared from bisbiguanidiniumcobalt(II) base, $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{OH})_2]$ and characterised from the studies of magnetic susceptibility, IR and electronic absorption spectra. Physical characteristics of complexes resemble with *cis* configuration.

Keywords : Biguanide, isolation, analogue, characterization.

Introduction

Both biguanide (BigH) (I) and ethylenediamine (en) (II) have identical donor sites and their complexes have thoroughly been investigated^{1,2}. From literature survey it is found that aqua hydroxobisethylenediaminecobalt(III); $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{2+}$ and $[(\text{en})_2\text{Co}(\text{OH})_2\text{Co}(\text{en})_2]^{4+}$ analogue of biguanide have not been reported so far. The preparation and resolution of dicynano complex $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{CN})_2]^+$ have been reported in previous communication². Now we report the isolation and characterization of some mixed ligand Co^{III} complexes with biguanide.

Experimental

Materials : Biguanide $[\text{C}_2\text{H}_7\text{N}_5]$ has been prepared as reported earlier¹.

Physical measurements : The UV spectra of complexes were recorded on Varian Model 2390 UV-VIS-NIR spectrophotometer and the IR on JASCO FT/IR-5300 spectrophotometer in KBr disc at Department of Chemistry (CISC), Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh.

Diamminebisbiguanidiniumcobalt(III)sulphate hydrate : $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{NH}_3)_2](\text{SO}_4)_3\cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$:

About 0.1 mmol of bisbiguanidiniumcobalt(II) base, $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{OH})_2]$ was prepared by the action of strongly alkaline (NaOH) biguanide sulphate solution with calculated quantity of cobalt chloride³. This base was transferred to 200 ml water in a round-bottom flask and was treated with 20 ml concentrated ammonia. The mixture was oxidised by passing a brisk current of air through it for 6 h with frequent addition of conc. ammonia. The silky yellow crystalline cobalt(II) bisbiguanidinium salt gradually dissolved to a red solution with a brownish black residue. This was filtered and the filtrate was neutralised with dilute sulphuric acid and kept in the cold for two days when red crystals of diammine-cobaltic bisbiguanidinium sulphate separated. The pure product was first washed with cold water containing a little ammonia and dried in air (yield 50–60%).

Aquahydroxobisbiguanidiniumcobalt(III)sulphate hydrate : $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{OH})]\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$:

The red solution formed from cobaltous bisbiguanidinium base above was taken in a flask and a brisk current of air was again passed for 4–5 h, when it turned violet with the separation of some brownish black precipitate. The precipitate was removed and filtrate was concentrated and neutralised with dilute sulphuric acid and kept in cold for crystallisation when needle-shaped violet crystals separated mixed with a small amount of orange-coloured crystals of cobaltic trisbiguanidinium sulphate. The latter were removed by crystallization from hot water. The purified violet crystals were then filtered, washed with cold water, alcohol and finally dried over calcium chloride.

Aquahydroxobisbiguanidiniumcobalt(III)chloride monohydrate : $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{OH})]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$:

The pure complex sulphate, prepared above, was digested with a cold concentrated aqueous solution of calculated quantity of barium chloride and BaSO_4 ppt. was removed. The filtrate on concentration and cooling overnight gave crystals of complex chloride. It was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried over calcium chloride.

Aquahydroxobisbiguanidiniumcobalt(III)hydroxide monohydrate : $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{OH})](\text{OH})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$:

When a freshly prepared hydroxoquo complex sulphate was titrated with 4 N KOH gave precipitate of freebase as needle shaped dark violet crystals. The precipitate was filtered at once and washed first with ice-cold water and then with absolute alcohol and was finally dried over KOH. The aqueous solution of the base, when heated to boiling, decomposes with the separation of a brown precipitate.

μ -Dihydroxotetrakisbiguanidinedicobalt(III) : $[(\text{Big})_2\text{Co}(\text{OH})_2\text{Co}(\text{Big})_2]$:

The μ -dihydroxo compound was obtained when the above dark violet complex base was heated to 80 °C. The substance lost 20.78% of water (calcd. water 20.70%) and the colour changed to deep violet.

Results and discussion

The elemental analysis of complexes correspond to the formulae shown in Table 1.

The bis biguanidiniumcobalt(II) ion is highly susceptible to oxidation in aqueous medium. In strong ammoniacal suspension the bisbiguanidinium complex gradually converted to $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{NH}_3)_2](\text{OH})_3$ which undergoes further substitution in hot aqueous medium forming $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{OH})](\text{OH})_2$. The same product was obtained by aerial oxidation of $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2](\text{OH})_2$. The hydroxoquo complex has been found to undergo dehydration and dimerised when heated above 80 to 90 °C forming dinuclear complex $[(\text{Big})_2\text{Co}(\text{OH})_2\text{Co}(\text{Big})_2]$. The dinuclear product $[(\text{Big})_2\text{Co}(\text{OH})_2\text{Co}(\text{Big})_2]$ when exposed in air further absorbs moisture. The diammine complex base and its salts are fairly soluble in water yielding rose red solution. The sulphate and chlorides of diamminebisbiguanidiniumcobalt(III) ion gave fairly conducting solution and their molar electrical conductance value in dilute solution (M/1024) $\lambda_m = 170\text{--}184 \Omega^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^2$ indicated their ionic nature. The aqua hydroxo complex ion $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{2+}$ and its salts are relatively less soluble in water but the aqueous solutions of chloride is conducting and conductance values of chloride indicates it as 1 : 2 electrolyte ($\lambda_\alpha = 210 \Omega^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^2$). The anhydrobase of cobalt(III), $[(\text{Big})_2\text{Co}(\text{OH})_2\text{Co}(\text{Big})_2]$ is

Table 1. Microanalytical data of complexes

Sl. no.	Complex	Colour	Analysis (%) : Calcd. (Found)					X ⁻ = anions
			M	C	H	N	H ₂ O	
1.	$[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{NH}_3)_2](\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Red	10.78 (10.84)	8.77 (8.70)	4.02 (3.99)	30.71 (30.65)	19.74 (19.70)	26.32 (26.46)
2.	$[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{OH})]\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Violet	13.50 (13.53)	10.98 (11.01)	5.03 (4.99)	32.03 (32.90)	16.01 (15.90)	21.96 (22.10)
3.	$[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{OH})]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	Violet	15.32 (15.40)	12.46 (12.40)	4.93 (4.85)	36.36 (36.00)	13.76 (13.00)	18.44 (18.60)
4.	$[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{OH})](\text{OH})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	Dark violet	16.95 (16.80)	13.79 (13.70)	6.03 (5.99)	40.20 (40.01)	25.00 (24.80)	-
5.	$[(\text{Big})_2\text{Co}(\text{OH})_2\text{Co}(\text{Big})_2]$	Deep violet	21.37 (21.82)	17.39 (17.10)	5.42 (5.30)	50.72 (50.86)	-	-

sparingly soluble in water but undergo hydrolysis with cleavage to yield original aquahydroxobisbiguanidiniumcobalt complex, $[(\text{BigH})_2\text{Co}(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{2+}$ as indicated by similar electronic absorption bands. The diamagnetism and spectral behaviour of these complexes are diagnostic to their oxidation state (+3).

Electronic spectra :

All the cobalt(III) complexes showed two distinct electronic absorption bands in region located around 20000 cm^{-1} (500 nm) and 28000 cm^{-1} (357 nm), similar to usual octahedral cobalt(III) complexes^{5,6}.

The electronic absorption band of $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{NH}_3)_2](\text{SO}_4)$ showed ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{2g}$ transition at 485 nm while aquahydroxo complex at 495–505 nm. The electronic band around 345–355 nm (medium and broad) is attributed to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{1g}$ transition in octahedral field for Co^{III} 4-6. The broadness and tendency to split into two bands of latter transition suggested *cis* structure of hydroxo aqua and diammine complex salt $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{NH}_3)_2]^{7+}$. The formation of μ -dihydroxo species on heating $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{OH})]^{2+}$ further substantiated the *cis* coordination of hydroxo and aqua group in the aquahydroxo complex base.

IR spectra :

The ligand biguanide sulphate $(\text{BigHH}_2\text{SO}_4) \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ contains =NH, -NH-, $-\text{N}^+\text{H}_3$ and SO_4^{2-} groups. The various mode of IR vibrations of =NH, -NH-, $-\text{NH}_3$ and SO_4^{2-} are observed in 3μ to 16μ region. The NH and NH_2 stretches were observed as broadband between 2950 to 3250 cm^{-1} . The ($-\text{C}=\text{NH}$) stretching band of the ligand is observed as broad band near 1640 cm^{-1} . The -NH-, $-\text{NH}_2$ deformation vibrations were located at 1400 cm^{-1} . The ionic sulphate group displays $\nu_3(\text{SO}_4)$ as broad and strong band at 1111 cm^{-1} . The strong and sharp band at 617 cm^{-1} is attributed to ν_4 vibrations of sulphate group⁸. The complex sulphate showed $\nu_1(\text{SO}_4)$ and $\nu_3(\text{SO}_4)$ similar to ionic sulphate group^{7,8}. The IR spectra of biguanide complex $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{OH})]\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ displays SO_4^{2-} group ν_3 vibration at 1093 cm^{-1} and $\nu_4(\text{SO}_4^{2-})$ at 615 cm^{-1} which is characteristic of ionic SO_4^{2-} group⁸. The complex shows broad band at 3416 cm^{-1} attributed to hydrogen bonded H_2O molecule. The sharp and strong band observed at 2924 cm^{-1} in the IR spectrum of complex $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{OH})]\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ indicated the presence of coordinated hydroxyl group. The IR band located at 1660 cm^{-1} in the complex is attributed to combination of bending band of H_2O and (NH_2) groups. The

IR band observed at 669 cm^{-1} in the aqua complexes is typical of rocking vibration of coordinated water molecule^{7,8}. The new IR band in the spectrum at 459 cm^{-1} can be attributed to (Co-O) stretching band. Thus on the basis of IR spectral studies, it is suggested that one H_2O and OH are coordinated and anions are uncoordinated in aquahydroxo complexes. The IR spectrum of $[(\text{Big})_2\text{Co}(\text{OH})_2\text{Co}(\text{Big})_2]$ displays a band at 2345 cm^{-1} attributed to μ -OH group in anhydro base⁸. The $\nu(\text{OH})$ of $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{2+}$ at 2904 is completely absent in μ -dihydroxo complex $[(\text{Big})_2\text{Co}(\text{OH})_2\text{Co}(\text{Big})_2]$. The bending band of $\mu(\text{OH})_2$ group were identified at 1095 cm^{-1} supporting the formation of $\mu(\text{OH})$ group on dehydration of terminal hydroxo group of $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{OH})](\text{OH})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$. The IR band near 460–470 cm^{-1} in the complexes were assigned to $\nu(\text{Co}-\text{O})$ band of coordinated hydroxo group⁸.

Conclusion :

From stoichiometry and above physico-chemical studies, the aquahydroxo complex $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{OH})]^{2+}$ and the diammine complex $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{NH}_3)_2]^{3+}$ are as mononuclear whereas $[(\text{Big})_2\text{Co}(\text{OH})_2\text{Co}(\text{Big})_2]$ is hydroxo bridged dinuclear species as shown below :

(L = L' = NH_3 and L' = H_2O , L = OH)
Aqua hydroxobisbiguanidiniumcobalt(III) ion

μ -Dihydroxotetrakisbiguanidinedicobalt(III)

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to my Gurudev Prof. S. P. Ghosh, J. N. Chatterjea and L. K. Mishra for their constant encouragements. Special thanks are to my loving daughter Anu Marisha (Manipal University) for typing the manuscript of the paper. Award of a Minor Research Project to two of the authors (R.K.P. and P.K.) by UGC (ERO), Kolkata is also thankfully acknowledged.

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